

NAVAL MEDICAL RESEARCH UNIT DAYTON

by

Respiratory and Subjective Adaptation to a Suboptimal Flight Mask by Naïve Users

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Abstract

Introduction: Physiological episodes (PEs) may occur in part because of a malfunctioning mask valve, leading to increased expiratory pressure. This might be particularly problematic if aircrew members subjectively normalize the malfunction and do not correct it.

Methods: Naïve and experienced flight mask users wore both an unmodified flight mask and one modified to create a faulty seal and increase the force necessary to exhale. We captured respiratory and subjective responses of the participants on the unmodified mask in a single exposure. We captured the same responses on the modified mask over multiple exposures for the naïve mask users, or in a single exposure for the experienced users.

Results: This study found changes in naïve users' respiratory behavior over time that indicated adaptation to wearing the modified mask. Naïve users' respiratory behaviors often changed over time to become more like those of experienced users. Subjective ratings of breathing difficulty also declined over time among naïve users.

Discussion and Conclusions: These results suggest that aircrew may unconsciously adapt to respiratory challenges over time and become less likely to perceive a potential problem. This raises the possibility that aircrew may tolerate suboptimal breathing conditions and potentially increase the risk of physiological issues in flight.

Introduction

Aircrew in multiple tactical aviation platforms sometimes report feeling impaired or unwell in the cockpit. Such events may be referred to as physiological events or physiological episodes depending on whether a fault is identified in the aircraft life support system (LSS) associated with the report. For simplicity, here we refer to these events and episodes collectively as PEs. Multiple causal factors likely contribute to PEs, but one possibility is that changes in the function of the inhalation/exhalation valves of the flight mask affect respiration enough to lead to symptoms, particularly if aircrew normalize such malfunctions and do not correct them. This study explored whether people may normalize suboptimal breathing conditions by characterizing the respiratory and subjective responses to malfunctioning flight mask valves of people who were familiar or unfamiliar with wearing a flight mask, and how unfamiliar users adapted to malfunctioning masks over time.

Regulator and Flight Mask Operation

Tactical aircraft use sophisticated LSSs to sustain performance and prevent harm from hypoxic or otherwise hazardous cockpit air. Gas travels in the LSS through a breathing regulator that feeds a breathing hose connected to a flight mask worn by the user. Gas flow in the mask depends on interactions between the gas supply to the regulator, the volumetric flow in some regulators, the pressure at the regulator outlet, the valves of the flight mask, and the respiratory patterns of the user (Robinson et al., 2022). Aircraft regulators are mechanical demand regulators that supply gas only when the pressure sensed in the breathing hose at the regulator outlet decreases below a set pressure, as during inhalation. Some types of regulators maintain slight positive mask pressure (i.e., safety pressure) to prevent inward air leaks.

Tactical aircrew in the United States Navy utilize the MBU-23/P flight mask (Gentex, Zeeland, MI), whereas those in the United States Air Force wear the MBU-20/P mask (Gentex, Zeeland, MI). These masks differ in some respects such as their communication wiring, but the shell and valves are identical (Gentex, personal communication; Shykoff, personal communication). The masks utilize separate inhalation and exhalation valves to ensure that gas flows only in the intended direction (i.e., that exhaled breath is not rebreathed, that cabin air does not enter the mask, and that supplied gas is delivered to the user rather than being vented outside the mask). Early in inhalation, pressure drops within the mask, causing the inhalation valve to open. This reduces the pressure in the hose between the regulator and the mask, prompting gas to flow from the regulator through the hose to the mask. Early in exhalation, the pressure in the mask increases and closes the inhalation valve. The closed valve causes pressure in the supply hose to increase, which stops the flow of gas from the regulator. At the same time, increasing mask pressure causes the exhalation valve to open and release the exhaled gas from the mask. In addition, the MBU-20/P and -23/P masks utilize a compensation tube that links the inhalation and exhalation valves to allow pressure from the inspiratory side to exert force on the exhalation valve. The pressure transferred through the compensation tube keeps the exhalation valve closed when the regulator is set to maintain a positive pressure in the mask.

Issues with Mask Valve Operation

Respiratory load is inherently higher when breathing through a flight mask compared to breathing ambient air. Some pressure is necessary simply to overcome resistance and move gas through the various hoses and valves of the LSS. This imposed respiratory load is negligible

when all system components are functioning normally, but it can become problematic when equipment issues occur such as malfunctions in the valves of the flight mask. As described above, proper operation of the inhalation and exhalation valves in the flight mask depends on changes in pressure and the movement of gas through the regulator, valves, and compensation tube. The flow of gas is altered when mask valves do not seal properly or when the regulator does not deliver gas as expected.

Many issues related to mask operation increase the difficulty of exhalation, but the exhalation valve is not always to blame. Instead, some of the issues are often attributable to the function of the compensation tube in the mask. When the regulator is designed to provide safety pressure, the compensation tube keeps the exhalation valve closed to maintain positive pressure in the mask. However, the tube also allows unexpected pressure deviations to propagate to the back of the exhalation valve and hold it closed, making exhalation more difficult. For example, the CRU-103 regulator (Eaton, Orchard Park, NY) can deliver a brief burst of pressure at the end of inhalation when supply pressure is inadequate, preventing the exhalation valve from opening immediately and causing spikes in mask pressure (Robinson et al, 2020; Robinson et al, 2022).

Counterintuitively, issues that prevent proper sealing of the inhalation valve can also increase the difficulty of exhalation. Mask valves rely on flexible disks that bend open to allow gas flow before resting against a plastic seat to stop gas flow. The seal may be compromised if the disk loses rigidity over time, fails to close due to accelerations in the cockpit, or is blocked by small foreign objects in the mask. Leaks in the inhalation valve allow pressure from the mask during exhalation to propagate back into the supply hose and through the compensation tube, applying additional force to the back of the exhalation valve. This added force makes the exhalation valve more difficult to open and can lead to excessive pressure inside the flight mask and greater effort to exhale. Prior research has examined the effect of faults in the inhalation valve on respiration. Unmanned testing by Camperman (2022) revealed that even very minute gaps between the plastic seat and the disk can cause notable increases in the pressure required to open the exhalation valve. Other research with human participants has found similar results (Robinson et al., 2025).

The Effects of Expiratory Resistance

Prior research suggests that expiratory threshold loads such as those generated by faulty inhalation valves can affect respiration. Although exhalation is typically a passive process, added loads can affect breathing patterns (Barrett et al., 1994; Erram et al., 2021; Goldstein et al., 1975; Gothe & Cherniak, 1980) and potentially fatigue the respiratory muscles. Expiratory threshold loads cause reflex activation of stretch receptors and abdominal muscles (Barrett et al., 1994; Davenport et al., 1981) and are associated with increased inspiratory muscle activation (Xiao et al., 2012), increased inspiratory drive (Goldstein et al., 1975), and increased initial inspiratory flow (Barrett et al., 1994). Expiratory loads can lead to increased tidal volumes and decreased ventilatory responses to CO₂ as well as increased respiratory muscle activation (Gothé & Cherniak, 1980). Barrett et al. (1994) similarly reported that large expiratory threshold loads can lead to increased tidal volume and minute ventilation, with a longer expiratory period. Expiratory threshold loads can also lead to changes in functional residual capacity and minute ventilation, but these effects depend on physical workload and tidal volume (Goldstein et al., 1975). Such loads also affect vital capacity and peak expiratory flow, although the clinical significance of these changes is uncertain (Erram et al., 2021).

The effects of these faults in the cockpit are not well understood, but researchers are beginning to examine these questions more closely. One recent study examined respiratory and subjective responses to breathing with a flight mask modified to prevent a proper seal in the inhalation valve, both at ground level and an altitude of 9,000 feet above mean sea level, in a hypobaric chamber. The study found that expiratory threshold loads caused by a faulty inhalation valve were associated with changes in pressures and flows in the breathing system and are a plausible contributor to PEs (Robinson et al., 2025). However, the changes in mask function associated with severe faults are readily noticeable by the user. It is not clear whether aircrew would be willing to fly with such masks in the real world without fixing them.

Normalization of Aberration

Humans are very adaptable in response to respiratory perturbations. Respiratory behavior changes in response to challenges such as acute hypoxia (Chiodi, 1957) and increased breathing resistance (Calabrese et al., 1998), for example. Just as humans adapt their respiratory patterns in response to various exposures, subjective perceptions can also be malleable. Breathing response and subjective breathing difficulty can both change in response to repeated exposures to degraded breathing environments. Previous studies examined the effect of repeated exposures to degraded breathing environments on breathing at rest (Eastwood et al., 1998) or during exercise (Amonette & Dupler, 2002; Forbes et al., 2011; Suzuki et al., 1995). They either measured both breathing response and subjective difficulty (Eastwood et al., 1998; Suzuki et al., 1995) or just breathing response (Amonette and Dupler, 2002; Forbes et al., 2011). Breathing response (i.e., tidal volume or minute ventilation) increased or stayed the same across the exposures (Eastwood et al., 1998; Suzuki et al., 1995; Amonette & Dupler, 2002; Forbes et al., 2011), and subjective difficulty decreased (Eastwood et al., 1998; Suzuki et al., 1995). These studies indicate that users' perceived effort may change over time as breathing patterns change during respiratory challenges. None of these studies used aircraft breathing equipment, however.

The Present Study

Findings that subjective breathing difficulty can decrease in response to repeated exposures to a sub-optimal breathing environment indicate that aircrew might normalize aberrations in the flight mask over time. They may tolerate suboptimal or even unsafe respiratory conditions if those conditions are not viewed as difficult or unusual. Anecdotal evidence suggests that aircrew may sometimes experience conditions in which their breathing equipment does not perform as intended but come to see these conditions as normal and tend to ignore them (Camperman, personal communication). Human adaptability increases resilience against unintended respiratory exposures in the cockpit but may also have negative consequences. If aircrew adapt their respiratory behavior or perception such that respiratory challenges are minimized, ignored, or even viewed as normal, they may be less likely to correct or report instances of suboptimal LSS function. Uncorrected aberrations in the LSS may make aircrew more vulnerable to PEs.

This study measured the respiratory patterns and subjective experiences of flight mask naïve or flight mask familiar subjects while wearing a flight mask that was normal or was compromised due to a faulty inhalation valve. We characterized changes in the respiratory patterns and subjective experience of the naïve participants when wearing the flight mask with a faulty inhalation valve over repeated exposures. We hypothesized that although naïve users' respiratory behaviors and subjective difficulty ratings would initially show a lack of adaptation to

the faulty mask compared to the familiar users, the naïve users would adjust their breathing over time in response to the faulty mask, and that their subjective ratings of breathing difficulty would decline over time.

Methods

Participants

We recruited 32 participants for this study, all of whom were non-smokers with sufficient fitness to sustain the exercise levels required for the study. They were assigned to either a mask-naïve or mask-familiar study group based on their prior experience with wearing a flight mask. Participants assigned to the mask-naïve group (n=20) had no prior history of wearing a flight mask. Participants assigned to the mask-familiar group (n=12) had worn a flight mask at least monthly on average over the six months prior to participation, or more frequently over a shorter time span.

Due to technical issues, we were unable to complete respiratory testing on the first visit for four of the 32 recruited participants; we do not report any data for these four due to the criticality of first-visit data for our analyses. The final data set used in our analyses reported here included 17 participants for the mask-naïve group (14 males, 3 females, average age = 32.7 +/- 6.0 years), and 11 participants for the mask-familiar group (8 males, 3 females, average age = 33.6 +/- 7.1 years).

Apparatus

Participants used two separate breathing setups for baseline and experimental measurements (described below). During baseline assessments, participants breathed room air through a Hans Rudolph silicone mask and series 2700 non-rebreather valve (Hans Rudolph, Shawnee, KS). The non-rebreather valve was connected to 1" tubing to minimize the resistance added by the apparatus during baseline measurements. The mask was secured to the face via Hans Rudolph harness straps. We measured gas flow using a Hans Rudolph pneumotachometer (Series 4830, flow range 0 to ± 400 L/min). During baseline assessments the meter was positioned between two lengths of tubing: one between the meter and the Hans Rudolph mask, and the other open to room air.

During experimental exposures, participants breathed through a standard flight mask (MBU-20/P; Gentex, Zeeland, MI), modified slightly to remove the in-mask microphone and add sample ports for the measurement of mask pressure and gas composition. The flight mask was connected to a CRU-103 regulator (Eaton, Orchard Park, NY) supplied with compressed breathing air at a minimum inlet pressure of 25 psig, managed via pressure controllers. The mask was secured to the face using a standard flight helmet (Gentex). Gas flow was measured similarly to the baseline assessment, except the meter was positioned between the CRU-103 and the flight mask during experimental exposures (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Experimental setup for modified mask assessments. Gas flowed from the CRU-103 regulator (A) to the flow meter (B) and then the flight mask (C). Sample ports are also visible in the mask. Photo by study staff.

We sampled gas in the mask using a mass spectrometer (MGA 1100 Analyzer, MaTech Services, St. Louis, MO) with the sample tube attached at the non-rebreather valve (for baseline testing) or inserted into the flight mask via the sample port (for experimental exposures). Pressure was likewise sampled at the valve or the mask, measured via ratio metric pressure transducers (SSC series, Honeywell, SIT, Fort Mill, SC). All measures of flow, pressure, and gas content were sampled at 100 Hz. Compressed gas delivery and respiratory measures were managed using a custom LabView interface.

Participants rode a cycle ergometer (Monark Exercise; Vansbro, Sweden) during portions of testing (described below) to approximate the respiratory demands associated with flight (Gordge, 1993).

Procedure

Participants characterized as mask-familiar attended only one experimental visit. Mask-naïve participants attended four visits. The first visit (V1) was the same for all participants. This first visit began with the participants providing informed consent and completing a brief screening/demographics form (see Appendix). Participants were then fitted for a helmet and breathing mask. Mask fit was assessed by ensuring the mask fitted comfortably around the nose/mouth and that a good seal was created with no leaks upon inhalation or exhalation when the valves were occluded. After adjusting the seat height of the ergometer, we began baseline breathing assessments using the Hans Rudolph mask.

Baseline assessments of approximately five minutes (Table 1) were conducted under conditions as close to no-mask levels of breathing resistance as our measurement methods allowed. These assessments allowed us to confirm that breathing patterns under normal conditions were comparable across study groups. During these baseline assessments, participants completed a subjective assessment of breathing difficulty before and immediately after donning the Hans Rudolph mask, at the end of baseline, and after removing the mask. They also completed a 30 second period of reading standardized passages aloud [The Rainbow Passage (Fairbanks, 1960); and Arthur the Rat (originally from Sellon, 1876)], to give a baseline measure of respiratory behavior during communication.

Table 1. Timeline of activity during baseline assessments.

Time	Description
Pre-mask	Subjective breathing difficulty
0:00	Subjective breathing difficulty
3:30	Read aloud for 30s
4:30	Subjective breathing difficulty
5:00	End
Post-mask	Subjective breathing difficulty (break for as long as desired)

After a break following the baseline assessments, participants donned the flight mask for their experimental exposures. Participants experienced two mask configurations, in counterbalanced order. The mask was either unmodified to function normally or modified such that the inhalation valve did not seal properly. The inhalation valve was modified by looping a wire approximately 0.029” in diameter around one arm of the inhalation valve, preventing the valve flap from properly contacting the seat (Figure 2). For this modification, the wire was positioned as close to the outer edge of the valve as possible to generate a gap of approximately 0.007-0.011” between the valve flap and the seat, resulting in the exhalation pressure required to open the mask exhalation valve approximating that of the CRU-103's relief valve. CRU-103 relief valve settings are allowed to vary between 9.6-25.4 cmH₂O, with maintainers most often selecting a range of 15.2-20.3 cm H₂O (Camperman, personal communication). The regulator used in this study had a relief valve setting of 18.2 cmH₂O.

Figure 2. Modification to the inhalation valve of the flight mask. The wire and small gap are visible on the bottom arm of the valve assembly. Photo by Dr. John Camperman.

Participants then completed a series of assessments using one of the mask configurations lasting up to 30 minutes (Table 2). Immediately upon donning the flight mask, participants completed a subjective assessment of breathing difficulty. Approximately every five minutes, participants repeated cycles of reading aloud, rating their perceived exertion from 6-20 using the Borg RPE scale (Borg, 1970), rating any subjective physiological symptoms using the Wong-Baker Faces Scale (Wong & Baker, 1988), and providing ratings of difficulty inhaling, exhaling, and breathing overall from 1-5. The first 15 minutes of the assessment were conducted at rest, whereas the second 15 minutes of the assessment were conducted with the participants pedaling the cycle ergometer at a pace of 60 RPM with a resistance of 1kp. Assessment periods continued to completion (30 minutes total), unless the participants requested to terminate the session or if their exhaled CO₂ exceeded 9.1% (indicating hypercapnia) or dropped below 2.9% (hypocapnia) for five consecutive breaths. After the end of the exposure period, participants removed the mask, completed an additional assessment of breathing difficulty, and reported whether they were willing to wear the mask during activities such as flying or driving. After a short break, participants repeated the same assessments with the other mask configuration. Mask configuration was changed by swapping the entire valve assembly; we did not alter the wire around the modified valve during the study to ensure consistency across participants. After each visit, the participants were asked several debriefing questions (see Appendix).

Table 2. Timeline for experimental exposure assessments.

Time	Description
0:00	Start; subjective breathing difficulty
3:30	Read aloud for 30s
4:00	RPE rating Symptoms Subjective breathing difficulty
8:30	Read aloud for 30s
9:00	RPE rating Symptoms Subjective breathing difficulty
13:30	Read aloud for 30s
14:00	RPE rating Symptoms Subjective breathing difficulty
15:00	<i>Start cycling (60rpm @ 1kp)</i>
18:30	Read aloud for 30s
19:00	RPE rating Symptoms Subjective breathing difficulty
23:30	Read aloud for 30s
24:00	RPE rating Symptoms Subjective breathing difficulty
28:30	Read aloud for 30s
29:00	RPE rating Symptoms Subjective breathing difficulty
30:00	End; Questionnaires

When the assessments were completed for the Hans Rudolph mask and the flight mask with both valves, mask-familiar participants were debriefed, thanked, and dismissed. Mask-naïve participants completed three additional visits (V2-V4) with a minimum of 24 hours between each visit. During subsequent visits, mask-naïve participants completed the same 30-minute exposure/assessment period as described, wearing a mask with the modified inhalation valve each time (i.e., they did not repeat the baseline or unmodified mask assessments during later visits). All mask-naïve participants were debriefed, thanked and dismissed at the end of their final visit.

Analysis

We analyzed objective measures of breathing and self-reported breathing difficulty, physical exertion, and symptoms. Respiratory outcome measures included mask pressures, end-tidal CO₂, minute ventilation, tidal volume, breathing frequency, and duty cycle. Our final data set included 28 participants with valid Visit 1 data (see “Participants” section); among these 28 participants, we excluded data from incomplete visits but included data from any completed visit even if the participant did not complete all planned visits (i.e., if a participant only completed Visits 1, 2, and part of Visit 3, we analyzed data from Visits 1 and 2). All respiratory data were examined using MATLAB 2023b. Respiratory data were examined for evidence of mask leaks, and all data were discarded for some or all blocks of a given session when a likely mask leak was identified. If data from a certain data source did not record on a given day, remaining data were still analyzed.

Activity Intervals

Data were grouped based on speech (quiet or reading) and physical activity (rest or exercise) for analysis. Respiratory data were analyzed from the at-rest and during exercise portions of the 30-minute visits. Quiet-at-rest data were captured at the approximate 2:30-3:30 and 12:30-13:30 minute time points, and quiet during exercise data were captured at the approximate 17:30-18:30 and 27:30-28:30 time points. Reading during rest data were captured at approximately 3:30-4:00, 8:30-9:00, and 13:30-14:00 minutes. Reading during exercise data were captured at approximately 18:30-19:00, 23:30-24:00, and 28:30-29:00 minutes. To help determine the analysis windows, the data were examined visually to determine where breathing-alone or reading ended based on changes in mask pressure.

Breath Cycles

An algorithm was developed in MATLAB to supplement visual inspection to expedite the distinction of true breathing cycles from artifacts. First, respiratory data were low pass filtered at 5 Hz with a 4th order Butterworth filter. The filtered pressure data were used to define a pressure difference signal as mask pressure – regulator output pressure. Negative pressure difference values were defined as inspiratory due to being directed inwards towards the mask, and positive values as expiratory. When available, the pressure difference signals were used to determine positive and negative zero-crossings, but given the constraint that the difference signal had to drop below a certain threshold (which was determined by inspection to be 0.3, 0.6, 0.86, and 1.2 cm H₂O for quiet at rest, quiet during exercise, reading at rest and reading during exercise, regardless of the mask type). When the pressure difference signal was unavailable, zero-crossings were defined using the flow data but without the imposition of a threshold.

Breath cycle markings were refined using additional constraints which were also determined by inspection. Tidal volumes were required to be greater than 0.19 L for quiet at rest, 0.31 L for quiet during exercise, 0.25 L for reading at rest, and 0.35 L for reading during exercise on the MBU mask, and 0.12 L during baseline measurements using the Hans Rudolph mask. The expiratory durations had to be 0.5s or greater in the quiet breathing data with one exception in which it was allowed to be shorter to allow expirations to be captured that otherwise might have been missed, and 0.6s or greater in the reading data. To help better mark the breath cycles, four lenient rules were added using the CO₂ measurements. CO₂ was required to exceed 2% sometime during the cycle. CO₂ had to drop below 1% breathing quietly at rest or 2.25% otherwise between 0.4s prior to the start of inspiration and the beginning of the next inspiration, or mask

pressure had to reach a negative value at some point during inspiration. CO₂ had to increase by at least a small amount (0.25% in reading at rest, 0.5% for all other activity types) from beginning of expiration to 0.4s after the beginning of inspiration but also decrease at some point during the cycle.

Respiratory Variables

Breath cycle markings were used to aid in the calculation of the respiratory outcome measures used in this study. To compute breathing frequencies for certain analysis windows (i.e., breathing data from 2:30-3'), starting and ending with positive z-crossings, breathing periods were defined for individual breath cycles and the means were determined. Inspiratory duty cycle was defined as the inspiratory time divided by the total time for individual breaths. Maximum, mean, and minimum mask pressure values were determined using single breaths. Maximum and mean mask pressure were used differently for breathing quietly and reading data. When breathing quietly, the expiratory durations were shorter, and maximum mask pressure is a useful measure given the pressure needed to open the valve. When reading, the expirations are longer, and mask pressure tends to fluctuate over time, making mean mask pressure a more useful measure. Tidal volume was defined for individual inspirations by integrating the flow data. Minute ventilation was defined for analysis windows using the tidal volumes and breath timings. Work of breathing, which was only used for data collected using the Hans Rudolph mask, was calculated for individual inspiratory cycles. To compute inspiratory work of breathing, pressure values were interpreted between the beginning and endpoints to form a baseline from which to subtract those computed during inspiration. Finally, end-tidal %CO₂ was defined as the maximum CO₂ value for a given cycle.

Subjective Data

Subjective breathing difficulty, Borg RPE, and subjective symptom/symptom severity data were measured just after the reading periods (4:00, 9:00 and 14:00 during rest, and 19:00, 24:00 and 29:00 during exercise).

Statistical Analysis

All statistical analysis was performed in R. To account for any potential differences between how naïve and familiar users breathed through the normal flight mask, we analyzed difference scores calculated by subtracting the single mean values from the normal mask data from the modified mask data values. All subsequent analyses and discussion for a given respiratory variable focused on these difference scores, reflecting the difference between breathing with the modified mask and the normal mask.

The first round of analysis consisted of three omnibus analyses. The first was a comparison between the naïve and familiar groups on the normal mask at V1. The second analyzed the effects of subject group and physical activity on the difference score data on the modified mask, relative to the normal mask, in the quiet breathing and reading aloud conditions at V1. The third examined the effect of visit on the difference score data on the modified mask for the naïve group in each test condition. Due to imbalanced data sets regarding the number of breathing cycles that occurred per minute of data collection, they were first modeled using a Linear Mixed Effects Regression (LMER) with subject group, physical activity, and/or visit as fixed effects, and subject as a random effect. Histograms of the residuals were examined by inspection to make sure that the LMER was the appropriate model for describing the data. Each

LMER was then subjected to an ANOVA, and η^2 was used to describe the effect size as the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable explained by the independent variable(s).

Post-hoc analyses were performed on the difference score data. In one of those analyses, difference scores for the modified mask were compared between specific visits for the naïve group for a given breathing condition at V1-V4. These data were analyzed using Tukey HSD comparisons using the “emmeans” package (Russell, 2023), and effect sizes were determined using the “effsize” function (Torchiano, 2016) in R. These effect sizes are described as “medium” or larger if $d > 0.5$, and “large” if $d > 0.8$. In another post-hoc analysis, difference score data captured at specific visits for the naïve group were compared to those at V1 for the familiar group. To perform this analysis, the dataset was constrained and an LMER model was constructed with one fixed effect (subject group) and one random effect (subject). To perform effect size calculations, η^2 calculations were made. All differences are designated as “significant” if $p < 0.05$, or “marginally significant” if $p < 0.1$.

We note that in some cases the data reported in the figures do not appear to align with the reported statistical results (e.g., confidence intervals may appear to contradict stated statistical significance). Data reported in the figures reflect raw means for each variable, in which the number of data points contributed by each participant varied due to differences in breaths per sampling period, etc. The emmeans used in our analyses average out the random effect of subject, accounting for the effect of different numbers of data points across subjects. These differences sometimes resulted in small disagreement between the raw means in our figures and the analyses based on emmeans.

Scatter Plots

Scatter plots were made to describe the relationship between subjective difficulty and respiratory data captured at different visits for the naïve group, using the modified mask. Regular mask data were not used for these scatter plots, so that raw data points were used, as opposed to difference scores. The correlations between respiratory and subjective difficulty data were determined to be significant when p was < 0.05 .

Results

Manipulation Checks

We first confirmed that baseline breathing was comparable between the mask-naïve and mask-familiar groups. Baseline breathing was not significantly different between the two subject groups as assessed by Tidal Volume, Minute Ventilation, Breathing Frequency and Inspiratory Duty Cycle (See Figure A1, Table A1 in the appendix for data plots and statistics). Subjective ratings of breathing difficulty were also similar between groups during the baseline period (Figure A2, Table A2).

We next confirmed that the amount of breathing restriction was minimal during the baseline assessment, and that the mask fault increased the difficulty of breathing relative to the baseline condition. Critically, the maximum mask pressure data on Figure A3 show that the pressure values were low for the baseline mask (0.8 and 1.7 cmH₂O for breathing-alone and reading), but higher for the normal mask (5.8 and 7.8 cmH₂O), and still higher for the modified mask (13.4 and 13.8 cmH₂O) (refer to the Appendix for statistics). Similarly, subjective difficulty was found to be higher for the regular mask ($\bar{x} = 2.0$) than the baseline condition ($\bar{x} = 1.0, 1.4$ depending on the time-point), and still higher for the fault ($\bar{x} = 2.6, 3.0$ depending on the time-

point), compared to the regular mask (Figure A4, see Appendix for further information about manipulation checks).

Respiratory Data

Maximum Mask Pressure

Maximum mask pressure is reported for periods of quiet breathing; mean mask pressure is reported in the next section for periods of reading due to more complex pressure waves associated with reading. Figure 3 shows maximum mask pressure data from the quiet (no reading) periods at rest and during exercise. Normal mask data from V1 are shown in the left of the sub-panels. When using the normal mask at rest, the naïve subjects experienced lower maximum mask pressures than the familiar subjects ($\bar{x} = 5.2$ vs. 6.4 cmH₂O; $F(1,23)=4.4$, $p=0.048$, $\eta^2=0.8\%$) (left sub-panel). The naïve and familiar groups demonstrated similar maximum mask pressures using the normal mask during exercise ($\bar{x} = 7.9$ vs. 8.3 cmH₂O; $F(1,23)=0.1$, $p=0.744$, $\eta^2=0.0\%$) (right sub-panel). Table 3 shows an omnibus analysis of the modified mask data from the quiet breathing periods during V1. It shows a strong but nonsignificant trend of physical activity, and a significant interaction between subject group and physical activity at V1. The experienced users generated a larger increase in maximum mask pressures than naïve users on the modified mask at V1 at rest, but both groups demonstrated similar increases in maximum mask pressures on the modified mask at V1 during exercise.

Figure 3. Maximum mask pressure vs. physical activity, mask type, subject experience, visit and time point within a visit. Difference scores between modified and normal masks (averaged across time-points) are shown in gray. Error-bars = 95% confidence intervals. “Normal” = normal mask, “Mod” = modified mask, “Naïve” = naïve users, “Fam” = familiar users. V_ = visit number.

Significant effects of visit were found for the naïve group, both when breathing quietly at rest ($F(3,1128) = 83.3$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2=18.2\%$) and breathing quietly during exercise ($F(3, 1542)= 58.34$, $p<0.001$, $\eta^2=10.2\%$). When breathing quietly at rest, naïve participants generated larger increases in maximum mask pressure from V1 to V2 ($t=-9.7$, $p<0.001$, $d=-0.83$) and again from V3 to V4 ($t=-7.8$, $p<0.001$, $d=-.66$), consistent with increases from V1 to V3 ($t=-7.7$, $p<0.001$, $d=-.67$), V1 to V4 ($t=-15.7$, $p<0.001$, $d=-1.33$) and V2 to V4: $t=-6.0$, $p<0.001$, $d=-0.51$). The increase in maximum mask pressures was marginally significantly different between the naïve group at V4 and the familiar group at V1 ($F(1,22)=3.80$, $p=0.064$, $\eta^2=0.8\%$). When quiet during exercise, the change in maximum mask pressure increased from V1 to V2 ($t=-8.8$, $p<0.001$, $d=-$

0.64) but decreased from V2 to V3 ($t=9.1, p<0.001, d=0.66$), consistent with increases from V1 ($t=-9.5, p<0.001, d=-0.54$), and V3 ($t=-9.7, p<0.001, d=-0.72$) to V4. The increase in maximum mask pressure was significantly different between naïve participants at V2 and familiar participants at V1 ($F(1,23)=3.88, p=0.038, \eta^2=0.8\%$).

Table 3. Omnibus analysis of maximum mask pressure difference score data on the modified mask during Visit #1.

	Σ^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)		η^2
Subject group	2.60	1	22	0.32	0.577		0.03%
Physical Activity	30.93	1	1039	3.82	0.051	.	0.35%
Interaction	488.19	1	1039	60.26	<0.001	***	5.46%

Note. Significance codes: 0.001: ‘***’; 0.001: ‘**’; 0.05: ‘*’; 0.10: ‘.’.

Mean Mask Pressure

Figure 4 shows mean mask pressure data, captured from the exhalations of the reading periods. When using the normal mask, the naïve subject group experienced lower mean mask pressures than the familiar group at rest ($\bar{x} = 3.3$ vs 4.3 cmH₂O, $F(1,24)=4.4, p=0.027, \eta^2=1.1\%$) and during exercise ($\bar{x} = 3.9$ vs 5.0 cmH₂O, $F(1,24)=4.4, p=0.029, \eta^2=0.6\%$). When using the modified mask, there was a main effect of physical activity and a significant interaction between subject group and physical activity at V1 (Table 4).

Figure 4. Mean mask pressure (during exhalation) vs. physical activity, mask type, subject experience, visit and time point within a visit. Mean mask pressure difference scores (averaged across time-points) are shown in gray. Error-bars = 95% confidence intervals. “Normal” = normal mask, “Mod” = modified mask, “Naïve” = naïve users, “Fam” = familiar users. V_ = visit number.

Changes in mean mask pressure varied across visit for the naïve group when reading at rest ($F(3,628)=42.6, p<0.001, \eta^2=17.0\%$) and reading during exercise ($F(3,986)=84.3, p<0.001, \eta^2=17.0\%$). When reading at rest, the magnitude of the change in mean mask pressure increased from V1 to V2 ($t=-4.2, p<0.001, d=-0.53$), decreased from V2 to V3 ($t=3.7, p=0.001, d=0.40$) and increased from V3 to V4 ($t=-2.4, p<0.001, d=-1.06$). Consistently, the magnitude of change increased from V1 ($t=-9.6, p<0.001, d=-1.19$) and V2 ($t=-1.5, p<0.001, d=-0.66$) to V4. When

reading during exercise, changes in mean mask pressure increased from V1 to V2 ($t=-5.7$, $p<0.001$, $d=-0.53$), decreased from V2 to V3 ($t=5.0$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.46$), and increased from V3 to V4 ($t=-13.4$, $p<0.001$, $d=-1.22$). The change in mean mask pressure also increased from V1 ($t=-14.2$, $p<0.001$, $d=-1.29$), V2 ($t=-8.2$, $p<0.001$, $d=-0.77$), and V3 ($t=-13.4$, $p<0.001$, $d=-1.03$) to V4 in case of reading during exercise.

Table 4. Omnibus analysis of mean mask pressure difference score data on the modified mask from Visit #1.

Reading	Σ^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)		η^2
Subject group	13.94	1	21.92	3.39	0.079	.	0.52%
Physical Activity	50.56	1	620.77	12.30	<0.001	***	1.89%
Interaction	64.42	1	620.77	15.67	<0.001	***	2.41%

Note. Significance codes: 0.001: ‘***’; 0.001: ‘**’; 0.05: ‘*’; 0.10: ‘.’.

Minimum Mask Pressure

Figure 5 shows minimum mask pressure data from the breathing quietly (top row) and reading (bottom row) periods. Minimum pressure did not differ between naïve and familiar subjects using the normal mask when breathing quietly at rest ($\bar{x} = 0.5$ vs 0.5 cmH₂O; $F(1,24)=0.0$, $p=0.847$, $\eta^2=0.0\%$), breathing quietly during exercise ($\bar{x} = -1.1$ vs -0.8 cmH₂O; $F(1,24)=0.3$, $p=0.593$, $\eta^2=0.0\%$), and reading during exercise ($\bar{x} = -3.4$ vs -3.7 cmH₂O; $F(1,23)=0.2$, $p=0.654$, $\eta^2=0.1\%$). We observed a nonsignificant trend for familiar subjects to have lower minimum pressures when reading at rest using the normal mask ($\bar{x} = -1.1$ vs -1.9 cmH₂O; $F(1,22)=3.1$, $p=0.094$, $\eta^2=1.2\%$). Table 5 shows an omnibus analysis of the minimum mask pressure difference score data for breathing-alone and reading from V1 when using the modified mask. The familiar subjects had larger changes in minimum mask pressure than the naïve subjects, especially during exercise, leading to significant main effects of subject group when breathing quietly and reading at rest, and significant or marginally significant interactions between subject group and physical activity.

Figure 5. Minimum mask pressure vs. physical activity, mask type, subject experience, visit and time point within a visit. Difference score data (averaged across time points) are shown in gray. Error-bars = 95% confidence intervals. “Normal” = normal mask, “Mod” = modified mask, “Naïve” = naïve users, “Fam” = familiar users. V_ = visit number.

Decreases in minimum mask pressure became larger with visit for the naïve group when breathing quietly, evidenced by a significant effect of visit at rest ($F(3,1136)=3.78, p=0.010, \eta^2=1.0\%$), and during exercise ($F(3,1547)=30.5, p<0.001, \eta^2=5.6\%$). When breathing quietly at rest, decreases in minimum mask pressure became larger from V1 to V3 ($t=3.1, p=0.012, d=0.26$) and V4 ($t=2.6, p=0.046, d=0.22$). When breathing quietly during exercise, decreases in minimum mask pressure were smaller at the first three visits (V1: $t=9.0, p<0.001, d=0.67$; V2: $t=6.5, p<0.001, d=0.50$; V3: $t=7.5, p<0.001, d=0.56$) compared to V4, and marginally significantly different between the first two visits ($t=2.3, p=0.088, d=0.17$). Decreases in minimum mask pressure were different between subject groups when breathing quietly during exercise at V1 ($F(1,23)=7.56, p=0.012, \eta^2=1.3\%$), and marginally different when comparing naïve V2 to familiar V1 ($F(1,23)=3.51, p=0.073, \eta^2=0.6\%$). As when breathing quietly, decreases in minimum mask pressure became larger with visit for the naïve group in the reading data at rest ($F(3,636)=8.21, p<0.001, \eta^2=3.8\%$) and during exercise ($F(3,987)=55.5, p<0.001, \eta^2=14.5\%$). When reading at rest, decreases in minimum mask pressure became larger from V1 ($t=3.3, p=0.005, d=0.41$) and V3 ($t=4.7, p<0.001, d=0.51$) to V4, but smaller from V2 to V3 ($t=-2.7, p=0.038, d=-0.29$). When reading during exercise, decreases in minimum mask pressure became

larger from V1 to V2 ($t=5.4, p<0.001, d=0.50$) and from V3 to V4 ($t=9.5, p<0.001, d=0.87$), but slightly smaller from V2 to V3 ($t=-2.6, p=0.048, d=-0.24$). Consistently, decreases in minimum mask pressure became larger from V1 to V3 ($t=2.9, p=0.18, d=0.26$), and from V1 ($t=12.4, p<0.001, d=1.13$) and V2 ($t=6.7, p<0.001, d=0.63$) to V4. The effect of subject group was marginally significant at V1 ($F(1, 21)=4.26, p=0.051, \eta^2=1.1\%$).

Table 5. Omnibus analysis of minimum mask pressure difference score data on the modified mask during Visit #1.

Quiet Breathing	Σ^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)		η^2
Subject group	27.62	1	22	9.38	0.006	**	0.89%
Physical Activity	5.24	1	1051	1.78	0.183		0.17%
Interaction	9.33	1	1051	3.17	0.075	.	0.30%
Reading	Σ^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)		η^2
Subject group	92.86	1	22	4.38	0.048	*	0.64%
Physical Activity	1228.35	1	627	57.94	<0.001	***	8.43%
Interaction	86.22	1	627	4.07	0.044	*	0.59%

Note. Significance codes: 0.001: ‘***’; 0.001: ‘**’; 0.05: ‘*’; 0.10: ‘.’.

Minute Ventilation

Figure 6 shows minute ventilation data. Minute ventilation was similar between groups using the normal mask when breathing quietly at rest ($\bar{x} = 19.4$ vs 16.9 cmH₂O; $F(1,24)=1.67, p=0.208, \eta^2=5.9$), reading at rest ($\bar{x} = 9.7$ vs 10.3 cmH₂O; $F(1,23)=0.1, p=0.716, \eta^2=0.3\%$), and reading during exercise ($\bar{x} = 19.1$ vs 19.5 cmH₂O; $F(1,24)=0.1, p=0.781, \eta^2=0.2\%$) datasets, but significantly lower for the familiar group than the naïve group when breathing quietly during exercise ($\bar{x} = 32.0$ vs 27.0 cmH₂O; $F(1,24)=8.0, p=0.009, \eta^2=19.8\%$).

Figure 6. Minute ventilation vs. physical activity, mask type, subject experience, visit and time points within a visit. Difference score data (averaged across time points) are shown in gray. Error-bars = 95% confidence intervals. “Normal” = normal mask, “Mod” = modified mask, “Naïve” = naïve users, “Fam” = familiar users. V_ = visit number.

Table 6 shows an omnibus analysis of the difference score data for the modified mask at V1. Experienced users increased their minute ventilation significantly more than naïve users when reading while using the modified mask. Minute ventilation was also greater during exercise than at rest.

Changes in minute ventilation were consistently small across visits for the mask-naïve group when breathing quietly or reading at rest, but the naïve V4 vs. familiar V1 comparison when reading at rest was marginally significant ($F(1,23)=3.03, p=0.095, \eta^2=5.4\%$). Increases in minute ventilation became larger with visit for the naïve group while reading during exercise ($F(3,162)=13.64, p<0.001, \eta^2=25.3\%$), with increases from V1 to V2 ($t=-2.7, p=0.043, d=-0.57$) and from V3 to V4 ($t=-4.6, p<0.001, d=-0.99$), consistent with increases from V1 ($t=-6.2, p<0.001, d=-1.33$) and V2 ($t=3.4, p=0.004, d=-0.76$) to V4. Familiar subjects showed higher minute ventilations than the naïve group in the reading during exercise data at V1 ($F(1,23)=5.68, p=0.026, \eta^2=9.9\%$).

Table 6. Omnibus analysis of minute ventilation difference score data on the modified mask from Visit #1.

Quiet Breathing	Σ^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)		η^2
Subject group	25.37	1	29	1.36	0.256		1.65%
Physical Activity	46.67	1	73	2.50	0.118		3.04%
Interaction	28.35	1	73	1.51	0.222		1.84%
Reading	Σ^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)		η^2
Subject group	112.12	1	23	6.48	0.018	*	4.48%
Physical Activity	402.85	1	113	2.33	<0.001	***	16.1%
Interaction	40.09	1	113	2.32	0.131		1.60%

Note. Significance codes: 0.001: ‘***’; 0.001: ‘**’; 0.05: ‘*’; 0.10: ‘.’.

Breathing Frequency

Figure 7 shows breathing frequency data. The two groups experienced similar breathing frequencies on the normal mask when breathing quietly at rest ($\bar{x} = 12.0$ vs 12.2 breaths/min; $F(1,23)=0.01, p=0.913, \eta^2=0.0\%$), breathing quietly during exercise ($\bar{x} = 15.5$ vs 13.9 breaths/min; $F(1,23)=0.77, p=0.389, \eta^2=2.7\%$), when reading at rest ($\bar{x} = 10.4$ vs 9.9 breaths/min; $F(1,22)=0.09, p=0.770, \eta^2=0.2\%$) and when reading during exercise ($\bar{x} = 13.3$ vs 13.9 breaths/min; $F(1,22)=0.31, p=0.586, \eta^2=0.6\%$). Table 7 shows an omnibus analysis of the difference score data for the modified mask from V1. Breathing frequency decreased when breathing quietly with the modified mask at rest, but not during exercise. A significant interaction was found between subject group and physical activity when reading, driven by changes in the familiar group when reading at rest vs. reading when exercising (compared to relatively stable frequency in the naïve group). We did not find any significant effects of visit for the naïve group, whether breathing quietly or reading.

Figure 7. Breathing frequency vs. physical activity, mask type, subject experience, visit and time point within a visit. Difference score data (averaged across time points) are shown in gray. Error bars = 95% confidence intervals. “Normal” = normal mask, “Mod” = modified mask, “Naïve” = naïve users, “Fam” = familiar users. V₁ = visit number.

Table 7. Omnibus analysis of breathing frequency difference score data on the modified mask from Visit #1.

Breathing-alone	\sum^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)		η^2
Subject group	2.83	1	22	0.42	0.524		0.54%
Physical Activity	27.81	1	69	4.13	0.046	*	5.37%
Interaction	1.15	1	69	0.17	0.681		0.22%
Reading	\sum^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)		η^2
Subject group	0.056	1	22	0.01	0.917		0.01%
Physical Activity	3.287	1	107	0.65	0.421		0.57%
Interaction	33.98	1	107	6.75	0.011	*	5.90%

Note. Significance codes: 0.001: ‘***’; 0.001: ‘**’; 0.05: ‘*’; 0.10: ‘.’.

Inspiratory Duty Cycle

Figure 8 shows inspiratory duty cycle data. When breathing quietly during exercise, a greater proportion of each breath was devoted to inspiration for the naïve users than the familiar users on the normal mask ($\bar{x} = 45.1$ vs. 40.3% ; $F(1,23)=7.17$, $p=0.013$, $\eta^2=1.2\%$). No other significant effects of subject group were found on this mask however (breathing quietly at rest: $\bar{x} = 49.3\%$ vs. 43.6% ; $F(1,23)=2.24$, $p=0.147$, $\eta^2=0.4\%$; reading at rest: $\bar{x} = 16.9$ vs. 13.4% ; $F(1,23)=0.61$, $p=0.443$, $\eta^2=0.2\%$; reading during exercise: $\bar{x} = 21.3$ vs. 19.3% ; $F(1,23)=0.04$, $p=0.837$, $\eta^2=0.0\%$). Table 8 shows an omnibus analysis of the difference score data for the modified mask at V1. The modified mask led to decreases in inspiratory duty cycles compared to the normal mask when breathing quietly at rest, but not during exercise; physical activity had no effect in the reading data. Experienced users had slightly increased inspiratory duty cycle when reading using the modified mask, whereas the naïve subjects slightly decreased their duty cycle when reading using the modified mask, particularly at rest.

Figure 8. Inspiratory duty cycle vs. physical activity, mask type, subject experience, visit and time point within a visit. Inspiratory duty cycle difference score data (averaged across time points) are shown in gray. Error-bars = 95% confidence intervals. “Normal” = normal mask, “Mod” = modified mask, “Naïve” = naïve users, “Fam” = familiar users. V_ = visit number.

Table 8. Omnibus analysis of inspiratory duty cycle difference score data on the modified mask from Visit #1.

Breathing-alone	Σ^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)		η^2
Subject group	0.00	1	22	0.23	0.640		0.02%
Physical Activity	0.88	1	1040	125.72	<0.001	***	10.8%
Interaction	0.02	1	1040	2.55	0.111		0.22%
Reading	Σ^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)		η^2
Subject group	0.03	1	22	5.89	0.024	*	0.91%
Physical Activity	0.00	1	628	0.91	0.340		0.14%
Interaction	0.05	1	628	9.69	0.002	**	1.53%

Note. Significance codes: 0.001: ‘***’; 0.001: ‘**’; 0.05: ‘*’; 0.10: ‘.’.

Decreases in inspiratory duty cycle were found across visit for the naïve group when breathing quietly at rest ($F(3,1132)=7.52, p<0.001, \eta^2=2.0\%$), but duty cycle tended to be stable or increase slightly with visit when breathing quietly during exercise ($F(3,1541)=6.61, p<0.001, \eta^2=1.2\%$). When breathing quietly at rest, small but significant differences were found from V1 to V2 ($t=2.8, p=0.029, d=0.24$), from V3 to V4 ($t=3.7, p=0.001, d=0.32$) and from V1 to V4 ($t=4.0, p<0.001, d=0.34$), and a trend toward significance was found between V2 and V3 ($t=-2.5, p=0.055, d=-0.21$). When breathing quietly during exercise, the change in duty cycle was slightly larger from V1 to V3 ($t=-4.4, p<0.001, d=-0.31$), and marginally significant differences were found between V2 and V3 ($t=-2.6, p=0.050, d=-0.18$) and V3 and V4 ($t=2.5, p=0.058, d=0.19$). We did not observe any significant effects of visit for the naïve group when reading at rest ($F(3,637)=1.36, p=0.253, \eta^2=0.7\%$) or reading during exercise ($F(3,989)=0.26, p=0.856, \eta^2=0.1\%$). We did, however, observe that naïve users’ duty cycle decreased when reading at rest whereas familiar users’ duty cycle increased ($F(1,19)=6.19, p=0.022, \eta^2=2.7\%$ for V1 naïve vs. V1 familiar; $F(1,26)=16.83, p<0.001, \eta^2=5.7\%$ for V2 naïve vs. V1 familiar; $F(1,23)=8.62, p=0.007, \eta^2=2.9\%$ for V3 naïve vs. V1 familiar; $F(1,25)=15.25, p<0.001, \eta^2=5.4\%$ for V4 naïve vs. V1 familiar). The naïve V4 vs. experienced V1 comparison was marginally significant during exercise ($t=3.7, p=0.068, d=0.56$).

Tidal Volume

Figure 9 shows tidal volume data. Tidal volume was not significantly different between groups when breathing quietly at rest ($\bar{x} = 1.6$ vs. 1.4 L; $F(1,24)=0.61, p=0.257, \eta^2=0.2\%$), breathing quietly during exercise ($\bar{x} = 2.1$ vs. 1.8 L; $F(1,24)=1.00, p=0.327, \eta^2=0.2\%$), reading at rest ($\bar{x} = 0.9$ vs. 1.0 L; $F(1,23)=0.58, p=0.456, \eta^2=0.2\%$), or reading during exercise ($\bar{x} = 1.4$ vs. 1.3 L; $F(1,24)=0.45, p=0.507, \eta^2=0.1\%$). Table 9 shows an omnibus analysis of the difference score data for the modified mask from V1. Significant interactions between physical activity and subject group were found in the breathing quietly and reading data, such that the familiar users increased tidal volume during exercise more than the naïve users when wearing the modified mask.

Figure 9. Tidal volume as a function of physical activity, mask type, subject experience, visit and time point within a visit. Difference score data (averaged across time points) are shown in gray. Error-bars = 95% confidence intervals. “Normal” = normal mask, “Mod” = modified mask, “Naïve” = naïve users, “Fam” = familiar users. V_ = visit number.

Table 9. Omnibus analysis of tidal volume difference score data on the modified mask from Visit #1.

Quiet Breathing	Σ^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)		η^2
Subject group	0.26	1	23	0.71	0.408		0.06%
Physical Activity	0.18	1	1092	0.51	0.477		0.05%
Interaction	3.14	1	1092	8.61	0.003	**	0.78%
Reading	Σ^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)		η^2
Subject group	1.41	1	23	4.65	0.042	*	0.64%
Physical Activity	10.47	1	675	3.46	<0.001	***	4.81%
Interaction	3.37	1	675	11.13	<0.001	***	1.55%

Note. Significance codes: 0.001: ‘***’; 0.001: ‘**’; 0.05: ‘*’; 0.10: ‘.’.

Increases in tidal volume grew larger with visit when breathing quietly at rest ($F(3,1129)=3.4, p=0.017, \eta^2=0.9\%$) and breathing quietly during exercise ($F(3,1539)=21.39,$

$p < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 4.2\%$). Increases in tidal volume were larger from V2 to V3 ($t = -3.2$, $p = 0.008$, $d = -0.27$) when breathing quietly at rest. When breathing quietly during exercise, increases in tidal volume were larger from V1 to V2 ($t = -2.7$, $p = 0.033$, $d = -0.20$) and from V2 to V3 ($t = -3.7$, $p = 0.001$, $d = -0.26$), consistent with differences in the V1 vs. V3 ($t = -6.5$, $p < 0.001$, $d = -0.46$), V1 vs. V4 ($t = -6.87$, $p < 0.001$, $d = -0.51$), and V2 vs. V4 ($t = -4.1$, $p < 0.001$, $d = -0.31$) comparisons. Increases in tidal volume did not differ between visits ($F(3,633) = 1.63$, $p = 0.181$, $\eta^2 = 0.7\%$) when reading at rest, but grew larger with visit when reading during exercise ($F(3,988) = 30.78$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 9.3\%$), from V1 to V2 ($t = -4.6$, $p < 0.001$, $d = -0.43$) and from V3 to V4 ($t = -6.4$, $p < 0.001$, $d = -0.58$), consistent with differences from V1 to V4 ($t = -9.4$, $p < 0.001$, $d = -0.86$), and smaller effects from V1 to V3 ($t = -3.1$, $p = 0.011$, $d = -0.28$) and V2 to V4 ($t = -4.6$, $p < 0.001$, $d = -0.43$). The increase in tidal volume was higher for the familiar group than the naïve group in the reading during exercise dataset ($F(1,23) = 6.32$, $p = 0.019$, $\eta^2 = 1.5\%$).

End-tidal %CO₂

Figure 10 shows end-tidal %CO₂ data when breathing quietly and reading. End-tidal %CO₂ was found to be similar between subject groups on the regular mask when breathing quietly at rest ($\bar{x} = 4.2$ vs. 4.2% ; $F(1,23) = 0.02$, $p = 0.880$, $\eta^2 = 0.0\%$), breathing quietly during exercise ($\bar{x} = 5.7$ vs. 6.0% ; $F(1,23) = 0.96$, $p = 0.335$, $\eta^2 = 0.2\%$), reading at rest ($\bar{x} = 3.9$ vs. 4.4% , $F(1,23) = 0.96$, $p = 0.335$, $\eta^2 = 0.2\%$), and reading during exercise ($\bar{x} = 5.8$ vs. 6.3% , $F(1,23) = 2.29$, $p = 0.143$, $\eta^2 = 0.2\%$). No significant effects were found in the omnibus analysis of the modified mask difference score data at V1 when breathing quietly or reading (Table 10).

Figure 10. End-tidal %CO₂ as a function of physical activity, mask type, subject experience, visit and time point within a visit. End-tidal %CO₂ difference score data (averaged across time points) are shown in gray. Error-bars = 95% confidence intervals. “Normal” = normal mask, “Mod” = modified mask, “Naïve” = naïve users, “Fam” = familiar users. V_ = visit number.

Table 10. Omnibus analysis of end-tidal CO₂ difference score data on the modified mask from Visit #1.

Breathing Quietly	Σ^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)	η^2
Subject group	0.05	1	23	0.15	0.699	0.01%
Physical Activity	1.04	1	1093	3.01	0.083	0.27%
Interaction	0.10	1	1093	0.28	0.596	0.03%
Reading	Σ^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)	η^2
Subject group	0.08	1	23	0.19	0.670	0.03%
Physical Activity	0.28	1	673	0.62	0.430	0.09%
Interaction	0.22	1	673	0.49	0.484	0.07%

Note. Significance codes: 0.001: ‘***’; 0.001: ‘**’; 0.05: ‘*’; 0.10: ‘.’.

Changes in end-tidal %CO₂ differed across visit when breathing at rest ($F(3,1120)=15.22$, $p<0.001$, $\eta^2=3.9\%$), with a larger increase at V2 compared to V1 ($t=-6.5$, $p<0.001$, $d=-0.56$) and

V3 ($t=3.8, p<0.001, d=0.33$), consistent with different magnitude of change from V1 to V3 ($t=-2.7, p=0.034, d=-0.24$) and V4 ($t=-4.4, p<0.001, d=-0.38$), and marginally so when breathing during exercise ($F(3,1520)=2.18, p=0.08, \eta^2=0.4\%$) for the naïve group. Changes in end-tidal %CO₂ also differed across visit when reading at rest ($F(3,620)=7.27, p<0.001, \eta^2=3.4\%$) with larger increases at V1 ($t=3.5, p=0.003, d=0.44$) and V2 ($t=3.8, p<0.001, d=0.42$) compared to V3. Changes in end-tidal %CO₂ also differed when reading during exercise ($F(3,987)=5.10, p=0.002, \eta^2=1.5\%$). When reading during exercise, the increase in end-tidal %CO₂ was slightly larger at V2 than V1 ($t=-2.8, p=0.025, d=-0.26$) and V3 ($t=3.5, p=0.002, d=0.32$). The difference in end-tidal %CO₂ was marginally significant between V3 and V4 ($t=-2.3, p=0.096, d=-0.21$).

Subjective Data

Breathing Difficulty

Figure 11 shows subjective difficulty ratings during inhalation. This variable was similar between the naïve and familiar users on the regular mask at rest ($\bar{x} = 1.5$ vs. 1.5 ; $F(1,26)=0.00, p=0.949, \eta^2=0.0\%$) and during exercise ($\bar{x} = 1.7$ vs. 1.6 ; $F(1,26)=0.03, p=0.867, \eta^2=0.1\%$). Table 11 shows an omnibus analysis of the difference score data from V1. We found a small but significant effect of physical activity, suggesting that subjective difficulty of inhalation was slightly increased on the modified mask during exercise. A significant effect of visit was found on the modified mask for the naïve group when breathing quietly at rest ($F(3, 177)=9.78, p<0.001, \eta^2=16.5\%$); difficulty increased at V1 but decreased at V2 ($t=3.94, p<0.001, d=0.78$), V3 ($t=5.15, p<0.001, d=1.04$), and V4 ($t=3.33, p=0.006, d=0.68$). Difference scores did not differ across visit during exercise ($F(3, 173)=1.80, p=0.149, \eta^2=3.1\%$).

Figure 11. Subjective difficulty of inhalation vs. physical activity, mask type, subject experience, visit and time point within a visit. Subjective difficulty of inhalation difference score data (averaged across time points) are shown in gray. Error-bars = 95% confidence intervals. “Normal” = normal mask, “Mod” = modified mask, “Naïve” = naïve users, “Fam” = familiar users. V_ = visit number.

Table 11. Omnibus analysis of subjective difficulty of inhalation difference score data on the modified mask from Visit #1.

	Σ^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)		η^2
Subject group	0.00	1	26	0.01	0.939		0.00%
Physical Activity	0.89	1	138	5.01	0.027	*	3.47%
Interaction	0.03	1	138	0.17	0.678		0.12%

Note. Significance codes: 0.001: ‘***’; 0.001: ‘**’; 0.05: ‘*’; 0.10: ‘.’.

Figure 12 shows subjective difficulty ratings during exhalation. This variable was similar between the naïve and familiar listeners on the regular mask at rest ($\bar{x} = 2.0$ vs. 2.0 ; $F(1,26)=0.02$, $p=0.902$, $\eta^2=0.0\%$) and during exercise ($\bar{x} = 2.5$ vs. 2.4 ; $F(1,26)=0.12$, $p=0.713$, $\eta^2=0.2\%$). Table 12 shows that there were no significant effects in the omnibus analysis of the subjective difficulty of exhalation data for the modified mask at V1. Subjective difficulty of exhalation differed across visit for the naïve subjects at rest ($F(3, 177)=10.3$, $p<0.001$, $\eta^2=17.3\%$), and during exercise ($F(3, 174)=13.2$, $p<0.001$, $\eta^2=22.8\%$). At rest, the increase in difficulty ratings was larger at V1 and V2, compared to V3 and V4 (V1 vs. V3: $t=4.60$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.93$; V1 vs. V4: $t=3.9$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.79$; V2 vs. V3: $t=3.8$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.79$; V2 vs. V4: $t=3.2$, $p=0.009$, $d=0.65$), and increases were smaller for the naïve group at V3 ($F(1,25)=7.17$, $p=0.013$, $\eta^2=23.9\%$) and V4 ($F(1,25)=7.69$, $p=0.010$, $\eta^2=21.7\%$) compared the familiar group at V1. During exercise, the increases in ratings of difficulty exhaling were larger at V1 and V2, compared to V3 and V4 (V1 vs. V3: $t=4.9$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.99$; V1 vs. V4: $t=5.4$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.12$; V2 vs. V3: $t=3.1$, $p=0.012$, $d=0.64$; V2 vs. V4: $t=3.7$, $p=0.002$, $d=0.77$), as well. We found significant differences between naïve V3 and familiar V1 ($F(1,25)=6.34$, $p=0.019$, $\eta^2=24.5\%$) and between naïve V4 and familiar V1 ($F(1,24)=9.21$, $p=0.006$, $\eta^2=35.6\%$) during exercise such that the naïve participants reported smaller increases in difficulty with the modified mask compared to the normal mask than familiar participants. In general, these data describe a pattern in which naïve users reported decreasing perceptions of difficulty exhaling across visit when using the modified mask.

Figure 12. Subjective difficulty of exhalation vs. physical activity, mask type, subject experience, visit and time point within a visit. Subjective difficulty of exhalation difference scores (averaged across time points) are shown in gray. Error-bars = 95% confidence intervals. “Normal” = normal mask, “Mod” = modified mask, “Naïve” = naïve users, “Fam” = familiar users. V_ = visit number.

Table 12. Omnibus analysis of subjective difficulty of exhalation difference score data on the modified mask from Visit #1.

	Σ^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)	η^2
Subject group	0.16	1	26	0.73	0.401	0.51%
Physical Activity	0.14	1	138	0.61	0.435	0.43%
Interaction	0.32	1	138	1.41	0.237	1.00%

Note. Significance codes: 0.001: ‘****’; 0.001: ‘***’; 0.05: ‘*’; 0.10: ‘.’.

Figure 13 shows subjective reports of the overall difficulty of breathing. Subjective difficulty was similar between the naïve and familiar users on the regular mask at rest ($\bar{x} = 1.7$ vs. 1.7; $F(1,26)=0.02$, $p=0.884$, $\eta^2=0.0\%$) and during exercise ($\bar{x} = 2.1$ vs. 2.1; $F(1,26)=0.01$, $p=0.937$, $\eta^2=0.0\%$). Table 13 shows the omnibus analysis of overall subjective difficulty ratings for the modified mask at V1. We did not observe any significant effects of group or physical activity. Within the naïve group, changes in overall subjective difficulty differed across visit at rest ($F(3,177)=12.55$, $p<0.001$, $\eta^2=21.2\%$) and during exercise ($F(3,173)=11.66$, $p<0.001$, $\eta^2=20.2\%$). At rest, increases in subjective difficulty were smaller from V1 to V2 ($t=2.92$, $p=0.020$, $d=0.58$) and again from V2 to V3 ($t=3.2$, $p=0.009$, $d=0.65$), and from V1 to V3 ($t=6.07$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.30$) and V4 ($t=3.7$, $p=0.002$, $d=0.75$). The difference between V3 and V4 was marginally significant ($t=-2.3$, $p=0.095$, $d=-0.48$). Increases in subjective difficulty were also found to be smaller for the naïve group at V2 ($t=5.4$, $p=0.028$, $\eta^2=17.9\%$), V3 ($t=8.8$, $p=0.007$, $d=1.11$, $\eta^2=38.7\%$), and V4 ($t=5.2$, $p=0.031$, $\eta^2=17.6\%$) compared to the familiar group at V1. During exercise, the increase in subjective difficulty was larger at V1 than V3 ($t=5.1$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.03$) and at V2 than V3 ($t=3.9$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.80$). Significant differences were also found

when comparing V1 and V4 ($t=4.2, p<0.001, d=0.88$) and V2 and V4 ($t=3.1, p=0.012, d=0.65$). The increase in overall subjective difficulty was smaller at V3 ($t=6.2, p=0.020, \eta^2=33.8\%$) and V4 ($t=5.6, p=0.026, \eta^2=23.0\%$) for the naïve group, compared to at V1 for the familiar group. In general, overall subjective difficulty was similar at baseline between the naïve and familiar groups at V1, before decreasing with visit for the naïve group to the point where they reported less difficulty with the modified mask relative to the normal mask than the familiar group.

Figure 13. Overall subjective difficulty vs. physical activity, mask type, subject experience, visit and time point within a visit. Overall subjective difficulty difference score data (averaged across time points) are shown in gray. Error-bars = 95% confidence intervals. “Normal” = normal mask, “Mod” = modified mask, “Naïve” = naïve users, “Fam” = familiar users. V_ = visit number.

Table 13. Omnibus analysis of overall subjective difficulty difference score data from Visit #1.

	Σ^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)	η^2
Subject group	0.21	1	26	1.14	0.296	0.81%
Physical Activity	0.06	1	138	0.34	0.563	0.24%
Interaction	0.00	1	138	0.02	0.891	0.01%

Note. Significance codes: 0.001: ‘***’; 0.001: ‘**’; 0.05: ‘*’; 0.10: ‘.’.

Physical Effort

Figure 14 shows RPE ratings of overall physical effort. Ratings of physical effort were similar between naïve and familiar users at rest ($\bar{x} = 1.7$ vs. 1.7 ; $F(1,26)=0.01, p=0.912, \eta^2=0.0\%$) and during exercise ($\bar{x} = 1.7$ vs. 1.7 ; $F(1,26)=0.03, p=0.856, \eta^2=0.1\%$). Table 14 shows an omnibus analysis of these data from V1; we did not observe any significant differences across group or activity level. Changes in RPE differed across visit for the naïve subjects at rest ($F(3,177)=9.60, p<0.001, \eta^2=16.2\%$) and during exercise ($F(3,173)=8.35, p<0.001, \eta^2=14.5\%$). At rest, changes in ratings of effort decreased from V1 to V3 ($t=5.0, p<0.001, d=1.01$), V2 to V3 ($t=3.1, p=0.010, d=0.64$), and V1 to V4 ($t=3.8, p=0.001, d=0.769$). The difference scores for the naïve group were also lower at rest at V3 ($F(1,25)=8.41, p=0.008, \eta^2=1.0\%$) and V4 ($F(1,25)=5.93, p=0.022, \eta^2=0.8\%$) than for the familiar group at V1. During exercise, changes in

RPE decreased from V1 to V3 ($t=4.9, p<0.001, d=0.99$), V2 to V3 ($t=3.3, p=0.007, d=0.68$), and from V1 to V4 ($t=2.7, p=0.040, d=0.55$). The naïve users reported smaller changes in RPE at V3 ($t=6.1, p=0.020, \eta^2=1.8\%$) and V4 ($t=4.9, p=0.036, \eta^2=1.5\%$) than the familiar users at V1. In general, changes in RPE across masks were similar between groups at V1 but decreased with visit for the naïve group, such that they were eventually lower than the values reported by the familiar group.

Figure 14. Subjective Difficulty (RPE) vs. physical activity, mask type, subject experience, visit and time point within a visit. RPE difference score data (merged across time-point within visit) are shown in gray. Error-bars = 95% confidence intervals. “Normal” = normal mask, “Mod” = modified mask, “Naïve” = naïve users, “Fam” = familiar users. V_ = visit number.

Table 14. Omnibus analysis of subjective effort (RPE) difference score data on the modified mask from Visit #1.

	Σ^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)	η^2
Subject group	2.68	1	26	1.95	0.175	1.35%
Physical Activity	2.17	1	138	1.58	0.212	1.09%
Interaction	2.55	1	138	1.86	0.176	1.28%

Note. Significance codes: 0.001: ‘***’; 0.001: ‘**’; 0.05: ‘*’; 0.10: ‘.’.

Symptom Severity

Figure 15 shows mean symptom severity scores for both groups at V1. Both groups reported minimal symptoms when using the regular mask at rest ($\bar{x} = 0.0$ vs. 0.0 ; $F(1,26)=0.40, p=0.531, \eta^2=0.3\%$) and during exercise ($\bar{x} = 0.1$ vs. 0.1 ; $F(1,26)=0.52, p=0.477, \eta^2=0.4\%$). Table 15 shows an omnibus analysis of the modified mask data from V1, showing a significant effect of physical activity in which reported symptom severity increased more relative to the normal mask during exercise. Increases in mean symptom severity were smaller across visit for the naïve subjects at rest ($F(3,229)=7.9, p<0.001, \eta^2=9.3\%$) and during exercise ($F(3,229)=4.7, p=0.003, \eta^2=5.8\%$). At rest, the increase was smaller than V1 at V3 ($t=4.6, p<0.001, d=0.81$) and V4 ($t=2.9, p=0.019, d=1.01$). The increase was smaller at V3 ($F(1,25)=7.18, p=0.013$,

$\eta^2=11.2\%$), and marginally at V2 ($F(1,25)=4.01, p=0.056, \eta^2=6.3\%$) and V4 ($F(1,25)=3.69, p=0.066, \eta^2=6.2\%$) compared to the familiar group at V1. During exercise, the increase in severity was smaller than V1 at V3 ($t=3.0, p=0.015, d=0.81$) and V4 ($t=3.0, p=0.015, d=0.52$) for the naïve group. Like subjective difficulty, changes in mean symptom severity decreased with visit for the naïve group on the modified mask. We examined two symptoms (dyspnea and increased depth/rate of breathing) in greater detail due to generally elevated severity ratings and their relevance to this study; these results are reported in the appendix.

Figure 15. Mean symptom severity vs. physical activity, mask type, subject experience, visit and time point within a visit. Difference score data (averaged across time points) are shown in gray. Error-bars = 95% confidence intervals. “Normal” = normal mask, “Mod” = modified mask, “Naïve” = naïve users, “Fam” = familiar users. V_ = visit number.

Table 15. Omnibus analysis of mean symptom severity difference score data on the modified mask from Visit #1.

	\sum^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)		η^2
Subject group	0.00	1	26	0.61	0.442		0.40%
Physical Activity	0.09	1	138	10.85	<0.001	***	7.19%
Interaction	0.00	1	138	0.75	0.744		0.07%

Note. Significance codes: 0.001: ‘***’; 0.001: ‘**’; 0.05: ‘*’; 0.10: ‘.’.

Subjective Difficulty vs. Respiratory Data

Figures 18-21 show scatter plots of subjective difficulty vs. respiration on the modified mask for both groups across the different respiratory conditions. Maximum mask pressure is in the upper-left sub-figures, breathing frequency is in the upper-right, tidal volume is in the middle-left, inspiratory duty cycle is in the middle-right and minute ventilation is in the bottom. Subjective difficulty of inhalation is in the upper-left of a sub-figure, subjective difficulty of

exhalation is in the upper-right, overall subjective difficulty is in the lower-left, and RPE is in the lower right.

Figure 18 shows data from breathing quietly at rest. Subjective difficulty of inhalation tended not to vary much with any of the respiratory variables at any visit, and for either group. Subjective difficulty of exhalation increased with maximum mask pressure for the naïve group at V1, V2, and V3 ($p<0.05$). At V4, the subjective difficulty scores were not affected much by the respiratory variables for the naïve group, aside from RPE increasing significantly with breathing frequency ($p<0.05$). The familiar group did show non-significant positive correlations between subjective difficulty of exhalation with maximum mask pressure and breathing frequency, but few other effects were found of respiration on subjective difficulty for this group.

Figure 18. Scatter plots of subjective difficulty vs. respiration when breathing quietly at rest across the different visits for the naïve group, and at Visit 1 for the familiar group, using the modified mask. Solid lines denote $p < 0.05$. Dashed lines denote $p > 0.05$.

Figure 19 shows scatter plots of data when breathing quietly during exercise. Subjective difficulty of exhalation increased with maximum mask pressure for the naïve group at V1 ($p < 0.05$). RPE was positively correlated with breathing frequency and negatively correlated with tidal volume, particularly for the naïve participants at V2.

Figure 19. Scatter plots of subjective difficulty vs. respiration from the breathing-alone during exercise data at the different visits for the naïve group, and at Visit 1 for the familiar group, using the modified mask. Solid lines denote $p < 0.05$. Dashed lines denote $p > 0.05$.

Figure 20 shows plots of the data when reading at rest. RPE increased significantly with breathing frequency and inspiratory duty cycle for the naïve group at V1 ($p < 0.05$). Subjective difficulty of inhalation increased with breathing frequency at V2 for the naïve group ($p < 0.05$). RPE decreased significantly with tidal volume at V4 for the naïve group ($p < 0.05$). The familiar

group tended to show similar trends compared to the naïve group at later visits, but subjective difficulty tended to increase with tidal volume for the familiar group.

Figure 20. Scatter plots of subjective difficulty vs. respiration from the reading at rest data at the different visits for the naïve group, and at Visit 1 for the familiar group, using the modified mask. Solid lines denote $p < 0.05$. Dashed lines denote $p > 0.05$.

Figure 21 shows scatter plots of the reading during exercise data. Subjective difficulty of exhalation increased significantly with mean mask pressure for the naïve group at V1 ($p < 0.05$), and relatively similar trends were found with respect to overall subjective difficulty and RPE, compared to exhalation at this visit for the naïve group. Significant correlations were found between mean mask pressure and minute ventilation and overall subjective difficulty, and between breathing frequency, inspiratory duty cycle and minute ventilation and RPE at different visits, for the naïve group ($p < 0.05$ in all cases).

Figure 21. Scatter plots of subjective difficulty vs. respiration in the reading during exercise data at the different visits for the naïve group and at Visit 1 for the familiar group, using the modified mask. Solid lines denote $p < 0.05$. Dashed lines denote $p > 0.05$.

Debriefing Data

Subjects were asked whether they would be willing to use the modified mask to fly an aircraft (or drive a car if they were not familiar with aircraft; see Appendix for a listing of questions the subjects were asked). Figure 22 shows a graph of how often naïve participants reported they would be willing to use the modified mask while flying an aircraft or driving a car

for each visit. We categorized responses based on whether they expressed full willingness to use the mask, stated they were willing but also listed caveats (e.g., no more than an hour, only without speaking), or stated they would not be willing to use the modified mask. The number of people who expressed unqualified willingness to wear the mask was relatively stable across visits. However, the number of people who expressed qualified willingness increased from V1 (two people) to V2, V3, and V4 (seven, seven, and five people, respectively). The number of people who said they were not willing to wear the mask also decreased from V1 (nine people) to later visits (five, four, and six people for V2, V3, and V4, respectively).

Figure 22. Frequency graph of naïve participant willingness to use the modified mask to fly an aircraft or drive a car for each visit.

Discussion

This study was designed to examine respiratory and subjective adaptation to wearing a suboptimal flight mask. Adaptation to challenging respiratory exposures may reduce the perceived urgency to correct the problem, potentially increasing the risk of adverse symptoms. We compared naïve flight mask users and more experienced mask users wearing both a normal flight mask and a mask modified to prevent a good seal in the inhalation valve. We characterized changes in respiratory measures and subjective responses over time in naïve users while breathing quietly and reading, both at rest and during exercise, using the experienced mask wearers as a reference. Observed differences between the naïve and experienced mask wearers at V1 and changes in respiratory measures across visit among naïve users both indicate that people learned to breathe through the flight mask over time, with corresponding decreases in subjective difficulty ratings.

Maximum, mean, and minimum mask pressure, minute ventilation, and tidal volume all differed between naïve and experienced users when wearing the modified mask during the first visit of the study. People who were familiar with wearing a mask breathed differently than naïve users upon exposure to the modified mask (and even at times when wearing the normal mask), suggesting that familiar users had learned how to breathe using masks and were able to adjust their respiration to the altered mask more readily than naïve users. Indeed, several subjects in the

experienced group anecdotally noted that the increased exhalation force from the mask modification was subjectively similar to pressure breathing they had experienced before. However, naïve mask wearers adapted their respiration over successive exposures to the modified mask. Maximum, mean, and minimum mask pressures, as well as minute ventilation and tidal volume all showed changes across visit among the naïve users under at least one of the test conditions. These changes indicate that naïve users adjusted their respiratory patterns over time in response to the increased breathing difficulty.

We also observed changes in naïve users' subjective responses to the mask. Subjective breathing difficulty ratings declined across visits, with corresponding decreases in ratings of physical workload and increased self-reported willingness to use the mask in the real world. These decreases in subjective difficulty appear to be driven by a decoupling of perceived effort from objective measurements. The scatter plots above demonstrate that in several cases the relationship between mask pressures and perceived difficulty became weaker over time. For example, reported difficulty exhaling was correlated with maximum mask pressure when breathing quietly at rest during V1-V3, but not V4 among naïve users. Naïve users' maximum mask pressures increased across visit for this group, suggesting that difficulty scores should have also increased, but we instead saw decreases in difficulty ratings over time. These decreases in subjective difficulty may have occurred because generating higher mask pressures altered the dynamics of the exhalation valve, because participants became less bothered by the sensation over time, or some combination of the two.

Implications

Humans are remarkably adaptable to different respiratory conditions, and the participants in our study were no different. However, this flexibility may be a double-edged sword in the aircraft. On one hand, adapting to transient or mild respiratory insults can help aircrew be resilient to respiratory threats. For example, the decrease in subjective breathing difficulty and symptom severity among naïve participants may have been due to participants learning to breathe on the modified mask more effectively.

On the other hand, adaptation to prolonged respiratory challenges may increase the risk of an in-flight event. Current tactical aircraft do not have monitoring systems to alert pilots to many physiological risks or abnormalities, leaving aircrew to self-identify issues based on their perception of breathing difficulty or symptoms. We found evidence that correlations between subjective difficulty reports and objective measures such as mask pressures and breathing frequency were often weaker during later visits for naïve users (and for the familiar group), suggesting subjective responses became somewhat dissociated from objective respiratory measures as people gained experience using the flight mask. Aircrew may become less likely to detect and/or mitigate problems in the gas delivery system over time if they adjust respiration to reduce discomfort or simply get used to the sensation of more difficult breathing. We saw some evidence of this possibility in the debriefing questionnaires when we observed increased willingness to use the modified mask during later visits compared to V1. Acceptance of suboptimal conditions may decrease aircrew margin for further adaptation and increase the risk of experiencing symptoms in flight if conditions worsen.

Limitations and Future Research

One limitation of this study that bears mention is that the mask modification was not subtle; the subjective effects of the manipulation were readily apparent. Several mask-familiar

subjects commented immediately upon donning the modified mask that something was wrong with it. One could argue that aircrew would not fly with such a mask and therefore the applicability of our findings to the real world may be limited. This is a valid point, but we note that aircrew are generally highly motivated to fly, the pressures to “suck it up” and complete the mission can be very high, and several participants stated they would be willing to fly with the modified mask.

We also note possible limitations of our respiratory manipulations (exercise and reading). Although these interventions were intended to mimic the increased respiratory demands associated with flight and communication in the cockpit, they may not have completely captured the dynamics of flight. Our results were also not always consistent across levels of physical activity or reading. It was important to capture the effects of different respiratory demands on these results, but this does make strong conclusions about how people adapted their breathing somewhat more difficult. This is not inherently problematic, however, as each manipulation imposed different respiratory demands on the participants and thus provided a more complete set of opportunities to describe respiratory behaviors.

In addition, we did not assess mask-familiar participants over time to see how they adjusted their breathing to the modified mask. The goal of this study was to address how users may adjust breathing over time to novel respiratory challenges, and we implicitly assumed that familiar users would already be adapted and thus less variable (and that experienced users had learned to breathe in a relatively optimized way to serve as a reference when evaluating naïve users). However, despite differences from the naïve users at V1 indicating some amount of previous learning in the experienced group, it is possible that experienced users would also have further adapted to the modified mask over time, leading to different additional comparisons and potentially different findings relative to the naïve users. For example, our results contain an apparent contradiction. Subjects who were familiar with wearing masks reported higher ratings of breathing difficulty than naïve users, but naïve users’ ratings of difficulty *decreased* over time even as their breathing patterns became more like those of the familiar users. It would be interesting to see whether the mask familiar users would report subjectively lower ratings of difficulty on the modified mask over repeated visits and the rate of any decline in perceived difficulty. We believe differing difficulty ratings between familiar and naïve subjects are likely due to prior expectations in the two groups. Familiar users knew how a mask *should* feel, and their ratings of the modified mask were likely anchored to that expectation. Naïve users, on the other hand, did not have any such expectations. The discrepancy between expectations and the experience of the modified mask may have led to higher difficulty ratings from the experienced users. We are currently pursuing research to investigate how prior expectations affect perceptions and the likelihood of a user noticing additional subtle respiratory challenges.

Similarly, we did not investigate how naïve users may have adapted their breathing over time when wearing a normal mask and whether we would have seen a similar pattern of results. We saw relatively few differences between naïve and familiar users when wearing the normal mask but did see some indications of different respiratory behavior (particularly during exercise). Future research examining how users adapt to wearing a normally functioning flight mask would be useful to better understand respiratory dynamics under normal flying conditions. Research to determine how long adaptation lasts after the cessation of mask use (i.e., how long aircrew “remember” how to breathe on the mask) would also be useful. The risk of in-flight events could conceivably be higher during periods of respiratory readaptation if there are significant gaps between sorties.

Conclusion

Respiratory threats in tactical aircraft can cause significant adverse symptoms in aircrew, disrupting operations and threatening readiness. In the absence of physiological monitors, aircrew must identify problems based on subjective perceptions. We found evidence to suggest that users adapt to wearing a flight mask with experience; naïve users may come to perceive respiratory challenges as less severe and their perception of breathing difficulty may become less correlated with objective measures over time. Our study specifically examined the response to respiratory challenges arising from a malfunctioning flight mask, but there is no reason to expect that users would not similarly adapt to comparable degraded breathing conditions. User adaptation to respiratory challenges may enhance short-term resilience but may also increase the risk of an in-flight event if adaptation reduces the perceived need for intervention. This research underscores the need to develop in-flight monitoring tools or other interventions to help aircrew detect and respond to possible respiratory threats.

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Appendix

Screening/Demographics Questionnaire

Participant ID:

Date:

Age:

Sex/Gender:

1. Have you ever worn a flight mask before?
2. If yes, please describe your experience with the mask (type of mask, frequency of use, etc.).
3. Do you have a history of any chronic respiratory illnesses (e.g., asthma, pneumonia in the last 12 months, lingering COVID symptoms)?
4. Have you regularly smoked or used vaping products in the last 12 months?
5. Are you in your normal state of health/fitness?
6. Is there a possibility you could be pregnant?

Debriefing Questions

Participant ID:

Date:

(If this is your first visit, please answer Questions 1 & 2 only. If this is not your first visit, please skip to Question 3.)

First visit questions:

1. Did you notice any differences between the two masks that you breathed? If so, please describe any differences.
2. Would you be willing to fly an aircraft (or drive your car) with either or both of the masks you wore today? If you would only be willing to wear one of them, please indicate whether it was the one you wore first or second.

Visits 2-4 questions:

3. Did you notice any changes today compared to your previous visit (easier or harder to breathe, etc.)?
4. Based only on your experience today, would you be willing to fly an aircraft (or drive your car) using the mask you wore today?

Manipulation Check 1: Baseline Comparison Between Naïve and Familiar Groups

The purpose of Manipulation Check 1 was to verify comparability between the naïve and familiar groups for the breathing variables of interest during the baseline period. We used ANOVA when allowed by the “anova” function in R (R Core Team, 2021), but t-tests were used otherwise. Figure A1 shows tidal volume, minute ventilation, breathing frequency and duty cycle between the two groups during the 2:30-3:30 minute period of the baseline assessment. The subject groups were not significantly different in any assessed measure (Table A1).

Figure A1. Comparison of basic respiratory characteristics for the naïve and familiar groups during the 2:30-3:30 minute period of the baseline assessment. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.

Table A1. Statistical analysis of the effect of subject group with respect to various breathing measures using the Hans-Rudolph Mask.

Measure	Test	P-value
Tidal Volume	ANOVA	0.730
Minute Ventilation	t-test	0.655
Breathing Frequency	t-test	0.676
Inspiratory Duty Cycle	ANOVA	0.928

We next evaluated how perceived difficulty of breathing compared between the naïve and familiar groups. Figure A2 shows subjective ratings of inhalation, exhalation and overall breathing for the 0:00 and 4:30 time points of the baseline assessment. Visual inspection of Figure A2 suggests a tendency of the naïve subjects to have reported more difficulty than the familiar subjects, but when ANOVA analyses were conducted with one fixed effect (subject group) and with time point as a random variable, there were no significant differences between groups with respect to any of the three examined measures (Table A2).

Figure A2. Comparison of subjective ratings between naïve and familiar groups at the 0:00 and 4:30 minute time points of the baseline assessment. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.

Table A2. Statistical analysis of the effect of subject group with respect to subjective difficulty using the Hans-Rudolph Mask.

	\sum^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)	η^2
Inhalation	0.15	1	26	1.44	0.240	4.23%
Exhalation	0.20	1	26	2.30	0.141	6.56%
Overall	0.12	1	26	0.98	0.330	2.85%

Manipulation Check 2: Breathing Restriction During Baseline Assessment and Effects of Mask Fault

The purposes of Manipulation Check 2 were to confirm that breathing restriction during the baseline assessment period was minimal, and that the introduction of the mask fault led to increased difficulty of breathing. Figure A3 shows mask pressures and WOB during the 2:30-3:30 minute period and first reading assessment for the baseline, normal and modified mask conditions. The left column shows maximum mask pressures. Maximum mask pressure was affected by the mask type during the quiet breathing period ($F(2,1206)=1517.9, p<0.001$), where it increased from the baseline mask to the normal ($t=-17.4, p<0.001$) and modified ($t=-53.0, p<0.001$) masks, and from the normal to the modified mask ($t=-31.4, p<0.001$). Maximum mask pressure was affected by the mask type during the reading period as well ($F(2,475)=504.3, p<0.001$), where it increased from the baseline to the normal ($t=-13.3, p<0.001$) and modified ($t=-31.4, p<0.001$) masks and from the normal to the modified mask ($t=-15.0, p<0.001$).

The center column shows minimum mask pressures. Minimum mask pressure differed across mask type during the quiet breathing period ($F(2,1214)=215.2, p<0.001$), where it increased from baseline to the normal ($t=-19.6, p<0.001$) and modified ($t=-16.6, p<0.001$) masks. Minimum mask pressure also differed across mask type during the reading period ($F(2,475)=480.3, p<0.001$), in that it increased from the baseline to the normal mask ($t=-3.7, p<0.001$) but decreased from the normal to the modified mask ($t=6.4, p<0.001$).

The right column shows work of breathing (WOB). WOB was affected by the mask type during the breathing assessment period ($F(2,1238)=60.5, p<0.001$), where it was elevated from the baseline to the normal ($t=-13.3, p<0.001$) and modified ($t=-31.4, p<0.001$) masks, and from the normal to the modified mask ($t=-31.4, p<0.001$). WOB was affected by the mask during the reading assessment period as well ($F(2, 480)=20.4, p<0.001$), where it increased from the baseline to the normal ($t=-6.1, p<0.001$) and modified ($t=-13.8, p<0.001$) masks, and from the normal to the modified mask ($t=-6.4, p<0.001$).

Figure A3. Comparison of mask pressures and WOB during the 2:30-3:30 minute period and during the first reading assessment between the baseline (Hans Rudolph mask; HR), normal, and modified mask conditions. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.

Figure A4 shows initial subjective difficulty ratings for the different conditions at different times during V1. Subjective difficulty of inhalation is shown in the left column. Inhalation difficulty was not affected by mask type at the 0-minute time point. A significant effect of time point was found for the baseline mask such that the subjective rating was found to be lower on average at the pre- time point (no mask) than at the 0-minute time point ($F(1,54)=10.9, p=0.002$). Visit was not found to be significant for the modified mask.

Subjective difficulty of exhalation is shown in the middle column of Figure A4. Difficulty exhaling differed across mask type at the 0 minute time point ($F(2,54)=26.5, p<0.001$) such that ratings of difficulty increased from the baseline to the normal ($t=-7.1, p<0.001$) and modified ($t=-4.6, p<0.001$) masks, and from the normal to the modified mask ($t=-4.6, p<0.001$). The difference from the pre- to the 0-minute time points was found to be significant for the baseline mask ($F(1,54)=9.25, p<0.001$). The impact of visit was found to be significantly significant in the modified mask data ($F(3,50)=3.1, p=0.030$), but none of the specific visits showed any significant differences.

Overall subjective difficulty data are shown in the right column of Figure A4. A significant effect of mask was found at the 0-minute time point during Visit 1 ($F(2,54)=18.3, p<0.001$), where the difficulties were elevated from the baseline ($t=-5.8, p<0.001$) and normal ($t=-4.2, p<0.001$) masks to the modified mask. The difference from the pre- to the 0-minute time

points was significant for the baseline mask ($F(1,54)=10.9, p=0.002$). The effect of visit was not significant for the modified mask.

Figure A4. Comparison of subjective breathing difficulty ratings for the pre-mask assessment (baseline) and at 0:00 for the baseline, normal, and modified masks. Modified data are shown for V1 alone and the average values across all visits. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.

Severity of Individual Symptoms

Figure A5 shows severity scores of Symptom C (“Dyspnea, air hunger, and shortness of breath”) for both groups at V1. This symptom is particularly relevant given the experimental manipulation used in this study and scores were higher on average for this symptom than others. Both groups reported similar low severity ratings when using the regular mask at rest ($\bar{x} = 0.2$ vs. 0.0 ; $F(1,26)=0.40, p=0.531, \eta^2=0.3\%$) and during exercise ($\bar{x} = 0.3$ vs. 0.5 ; $F(1,26)=0.98, p=0.331, \eta^2=0.7\%$), and no effects were found in the omnibus analysis for the modified mask at V1 (Table A3). Changes in symptom severity varied across visit for the naïve subjects at rest ($F(3,229)=3.68, p=0.013, \eta^2=4.5\%$), where a trend for a decrease was observed from V2 to V3 ($t=2.4, p=0.067, d=0.50$) and the increase was larger from V3 to V4 ($t=-3.1, p=0.013, d=-1.05$). Changes in severity did not differ across visit during exercise. We observed a trend for the increase in severity to be smaller at rest for the naïve group at V3 compared to the familiar group at V1 ($F(1,25)=3.71, p=0.065, \eta^2=6.1\%$). In general, the naïve subjects did not show a decline in the severity of this symptom with visit on the modified mask, and the familiar group showed higher severity than the naïve group.

Figure A5. Severity of Symptom C (dyspnea, air hunger and shortness of breath) vs. physical activity, mask type, subject experience, visit and time point within a visit. Difference score data (averaged across time points) are shown in gray. Error-bars = 95% confidence intervals. “Normal” = normal mask, “Mod” = modified mask, “Naïve” = naïve users, “Fam” = familiar users. V₁ = visit number.

Table A3. Omnibus analysis of severity of Symptom C difference score data on the modified mask from Visit #1.

	\sum^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)	η^2
Subject group	0.57	1	26	1.33	0.259	0.40%
Physical Activity	0.02	1	138	0.05	0.824	0.01%
Interaction	0.01	1	138	0.03	0.825	0.01%

Figure A6 shows severities of Symptom D (“Increased depth or rate of breathing”). This symptom, like Symptom C, was particularly relevant and was associated with higher-than-average severity scores. The naïve and familiar subjects reported similar low severity ratings of this symptom on the normal mask at rest ($\bar{x} = 0.1$ vs. 0.3 ; $F(1,26)=0.23$, $p=0.630$, $\eta^2=0.2\%$) and during exercise ($\bar{x} = 0.4$ vs. 1.1 ; $F(1,26)=0.02$, $p=0.866$, $\eta^2=0.0\%$) at V1. Table A4 shows an omnibus analysis of the difference score data for the modified mask at V1. We observed a significant interaction between subject group and physical activity, driven by a large increase in severity among naïve subjects during exercise on the modified mask. Increases in reported severity of Symptom D did not differ across visit at rest for the naïve subjects, but changed with visit during exercise ($F(3,229)=3.25$, $p=0.022$, $\eta^2=2.4\%$), such that the increase was smaller from V1 to V4 ($t=2.7$, $p=0.013$, $d=0.34$). Consistent with the other subjective metrics, the symptom severity scores were relatively high in the familiar subjects, compared to the naïve subjects.

Figure A6. Severity of Symptom D (increased depth and/or rate of breathing) vs. physical activity, mask type, subject experience, visit and time point within a visit. Difference score data (averaged across time-point within visit) are shown in gray. Error-bars = 95% confidence intervals. “Normal” = normal mask, “Mod” = modified mask, “Naïve” = naïve users, “Fam” = familiar users. V_ = visit number.

Table A4. Omnibus analysis of severity of Symptom D difference score data on the modified mask from Visit #1.

	\sum^2	Num DF	Den DF	F value	Pr(>F)		η^2
Subject group	0.13	1	26	0.31	0.580		0.21%
Physical Activity	0.05	1	138	0.01	0.917		0.01%
Interaction	3.33	1	138	7.63	0.006	*	5.16%

Note. Significance codes: 0.001: ‘***’; 0.001: ‘**’; 0.05: ‘*’; 0.10: ‘.’.